

E-CAM Software Porting and Benchmarking Data IV

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the current document is to deliver a joint technical report on results of the porting and optimisation of 8 new E-CAM modules to massively parallel machines and their benchmarking and scaling on a variety of architectures. The development of the modules was done in the context of the E-CAM program of Extended Software Development Workshop (ESDW) events.

In the deliverable, we outline the general workflow of the E-CAM programmers (which are distinct from the PDRA members of the scientific work packages of WPs 1-4) to address these objectives. This workflow includes:

- reproducible and efficient software builds (via EasyBuild),
- benchmarking (via JUBE),
- optimisation (via Scalasca).

In the case of EasyBuild, E-CAM Work Package (WP)7 ("Hardware considerations and the PRACE relationship") continues to make significant contributions to this open source tool in order to facilitate and investigate the portability of our applications. We highlight the most significant of these contributions:

- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1729](#) and [EasyBuild Merge Request 8284](#) enable GPU offloading within Clang if CUDA is included as a dependency;
- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1717](#) adds support for building the Clang C++ standard library as part of the installation, and for using the Clang implementation of run-time type identification (RTTI)
- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1716](#) and [EasyBuild Merge Request 8335](#) add support for the LLVM-based Fortran compiler Flang to EasyBuild
- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1744](#) introduces the ability to catch errors by in the SciPy and NumPy test suites.

With regards to the E-CAM modules produced in the research WPs, we include the following modules and related analysis for

- Classical Molecular Dynamics:
[jobqueue_features](#), an High Throughput Computing library developed by E-CAM. The associated modules relate to the development of more sophisticated support for Python-based MPI-enabled tasks ([WP1 Merge Request 237](#)) and support for additional MPI runtimes to make the library a more portable solution between HPC systems ([WP1 Merge Request 249](#)). These were developed in the context of the ESDW "[Intelligent High Throughput Computing for Scientific Applications](#)" and an ongoing collaboration with PRACE via a successful PRACE Type C Preparatory Access Project.
- Electronic Structure:
The development of the PANNA toolkit to create a neural network model using TensorFlow and leveraging input from an ab initio code such as Quantum Espresso, which can be used as a potential by a classical MD code such as LAMMPS. We reference the [neural network training module \(WP2 Merge Request 223\)](#) and the [neural network evaluation module \(WP2 Merge Request 220\)](#) which represent how the PANNA toolkit benefits from the optimisation and hardware-flexibility of the underlying TensorFlow engine which allows it to be used on multiple CPU/GPU/TPU systems, making it possible to develop and optimise neural network models based on large datasets.
- Meso- and Multi-scale Modelling:
We include the benchmarking DL_MESO on multi-GPU nodes up to 4096 GPUs ([WP4 Merge Request 78](#)) and the use of the E-CAM load balancing library [ALL](#) library for improved load balancing in DL_MESO ([WP4 Merge Request 180](#)).
We also include a [ParaDiS](#) case study, the reference modules of which are the development of an [extension of the ParaDiS DDD code where dislocation/precipitate interactions are included](#) and the [optimisation of ParaDiS for the Cray XC40 cluster at CSC](#) in Finland (both of these modules are part of [WP4 Merge Request 38](#) in the E-CAM library).

For the [jobqueue_features](#) library, we show that the overhead of the implementation is extremely low (as little as 10ms) and is highly scalable with respect to the task count in the High Throughput Computing (HTC) workload. This also highlights the persistent and effective collaboration between E-CAM and PRACE.

Another significant success story has been the multi-GPU developments undertaken for [DL_MESO_DPD](#). This has been shown to be scalable out to 4096 [Tesla P100](#) GPUs, which is equivalent to almost 20 Petaflops of raw double precision compute performance. This is facilitated by the incorporation of the [ALL](#) library for improved load balancing. The improved load balancing not only improves performance, but also scalability and memory management since it

inhibits the excessive accumulation of particles on any particular GPU (which can exceed the memory capabilities of the affected GPU for sufficiently large systems).

1 Introduction

The purpose of the current deliverable is to present a joint technical report on results of porting and optimisation of at least 8 modules which were developed in relation to the ESDW events concerned with massively parallel machines, and the benchmarking and scaling of at least 8 modules out of those related to the ESDW events on a variety of architectures.

Associated applications have been ported to new architectures by leveraging [EasyBuild](#) (the tool that delivers compiler/hardware portability for E-CAM applications) where the installation and dependency tree of the applications were optimised (described in Section 3). Increasing importance is being given to the handling of application "dependency hell", i.e., trying to provide a self-consistent software stack for multiple applications.

The modules and applications were then benchmarked on the High Performance Computing (HPC) resources available to the project and scaling plots were generated for a variety of relevant systems and architectures (as detailed in Section 4).

While being part of an overall series, this deliverable is intended to stand alone (Section 2, in particular, includes only minor updates to the workflow that was originally described in Deliverable 7.2[2]).

In this deliverable, we have chosen to include software applications from three research WPs (of which there are 4) where a minimum of 1 module developed in relation to an ESDW targets each application.

2 Workflow

In this section we describe the workflow of the programming team which is led by the Software Manager (at partner Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC)) and includes the programmers hired within the project in the context of WP7 (which are distinct from the Post-doctoral Research Associate (PDRA) members of the scientific work packages of WPs 1-4). We also discuss the interplay between the services that E-CAM can offer, the tools that are used and the applications of the E-CAM community.

The essential elements in the workflow are:

- reproducible and efficient software builds,
- benchmarking,
- optimisation.

The implementation and tuning of this workflow is an ongoing process and requires significant collaboration with the organisers of ESDW events.

2.1 Tools

Each element of the workflow involves a different tool. At each stage there are multiple choices of tools but we choose within E-CAM to use only a single option (while maintaining awareness of other possibilities). When describing each tool here we also describe the context of its use.

2.1.1 Software Builds - EasyBuild

In order for the information that we gather to be useful to our end user community, that community needs to be able to easily reproduce a similarly optimised build of the software. [EasyBuild](#) is a software build and installation framework that allows the management of (scientific) software on HPC systems in an efficient way. The main motivations for using the tool within E-CAM are that it

- provides a *flexible framework* for building/installing (scientific) software,
- fully automates software builds,
- allows for easily reproducing previous builds,
- keeps the software build recipes/specifications simple and human-readable,
- enables *collaboration* with the application developers and the wider HPC community,
- provides an automated *dependency resolution* process.

[EasyBuild](#) currently supports cluster and Cray supercomputing systems (Intel, IBM, Power and ARM architectures), with limited support for BG/Q systems (this limitation is no longer significant since the architecture is no longer developed).

In our use case, we aim to produce a build of the software under study with an open source toolset (GCC compiler, OpenMPI MPI implementation, open source math libraries) for use by the community and the build procedures are described in sufficient detail in the E-CAM modules associated to the software package.

2.1.2 Benchmarking - JUBE

Automating benchmarks is important for reproducibility and hence comparability between builds of software, which is the major goal. Furthermore, managing different combinations of parameters is error-prone and often results in significant amounts of work especially if the parameter space becomes large.

In order to alleviate these problems [JUBE](#) helps to perform and analyse benchmarks in a systematic way. It allows the creation of custom work flows that can be adapted to new architectures.

For each benchmark application the benchmark data is written out in a particular format that enables JUBE to deduce the desired information. This data can be parsed by automatic pre- and post-processing scripts that draw information, and store it more densely for manual interpretation.

The JUBE benchmarking environment provides a script based framework to easily create benchmark sets, run those sets on different computer systems and evaluate the results.

Where relevant, we will use JUBE to provide a means for the community to evaluate the performance of their build of the software under study.

We are also considering the adoption of [ReFrame](#) which is a Python framework for writing regression tests for HPC systems.

Collaborations with [EoCoE](#) and [FocusCoE](#)

The E-CAM programmers and software manager attended the [3rd EoCoE/POP Workshop on Performance Analysis](#) in Barcelona. We have decided to adopt the JUBE performance evaluation workflow that EoCoE has created with appropriate adaptations to the needs of E-CAM.

2.1.3 Optimisation - Scalasca

Figure 1: A Performance Optimisation Loop

[Scalasca](#) is a software tool that supports the performance optimisation of parallel programs by measuring and analyzing their runtime behavior. The analysis identifies potential performance bottlenecks – in particular those concerning communication and synchronization – and offers guidance in exploring their causes.

The Scalasca Trace Tools developed at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre are a collection of trace-based performance analysis tools that have been specifically designed for use on large-scale systems such as the IBM Blue Gene series or Cray XT and successors, but also suitable for smaller HPC platforms. While the current focus is on applications using MPI, OpenMP, POSIX threads, or hybrid parallelization schemes, support for other parallel programming paradigms may be added in the future. A distinctive feature of the Scalasca Trace Tools is its scalable automatic trace-analysis component which provides the ability to identify wait states that occur, for example, as a result of unevenly distributed workloads.

Scalasca is used as part of the JUBE performance evaluation workflow mentioned in the previous section.

Collaboration with [POP](#)

In addition to our own optimisation efforts we have been engaged with the [POP Centre of Excellence](#) for their support on two of the applications that appeared in previous iterations of this deliverable: PaPIM and ESPReso++. Further details are included where relevant (and all previous iterations of this deliverable are available on the E-CAM website at <https://www.e-cam2020.eu/deliverables/>).

2.2 Interplay with ESDWs

As described in the [ESDW guidelines](#) (updated in Deliverable D5.4[3]), it is expected that the applications to be used in ESDW events are known 2 months in advance of the workshop. The programmers role in the months prior to the ESDW is to gain some familiarity with these applications. The programmers will put in place a performance analysis workflow for the applications using the tools described in Section 2.1.

During the ESDW, the programmers are there to provide instruction and support in the tools and assist the participants where necessary. They can also leverage the performance analysis workflow that they have prepared to help analyse the performance impact of the work undertaken during the ESDW (using the HPC resources to which E-CAM has access).

3 Porting and Optimisation

This section covers the hardware resources available for WP7 "Hardware considerations and the PRACE relationship" and some specifics of the porting effort required on these architectures.

The HPC resources available to E-CAM to date have come from either one of the HPC partners of the project or from Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE).

3.1 Available Resources

3.1.1 Primary Resources

A number of HPC sites are project partners and have generously made development resources available to the project, particularly in the case where a particular HPC architecture component was not already available to the project. In the current deliverable, the primary resource has been

- [JURECA](#) (cluster with GPU accelerators and KNL booster, through partner FZJ-JSC)

for general development work.

3.1.2 PRACE Resources

In the case of PRACE resources, there are two main avenues for access to resources. Each Centre of Excellence (CoE), such as E-CAM, has been allocated 0.5% of the production resource budget of PRACE. The second avenue is the normal PRACE [Preparatory Access Call](#) process. E-CAM has been successful three times in acquiring additional resources through this second avenue, making an additional 1.55M core hours available to the project.

We provide the complete list of supercomputers available through PRACE here (the configuration details of the hardware are available in the [PRACE Project Access Terms of Reference](#)):

- Marconi Broadwell, 180.000 core hours
- Marconi KNL, 3.050.000 core hours
- Joliot Curie AMD, 1.715.000 core hours
- Joliot Curie KNL, 470.000 core hours
- Joliot Curie SKL, 660.000 core hours
- JUWELS, 350.000 core hours
- Hawk, 2.300.000 core hours
- MareNostrum4, 1.200.000 core hours
- Piz Daint, 2.720.000 core hours, 40.000 node hours

For 2019/2020, we have requested access to Joliot-Curie, JUWELS, Piz-Daint and Marenostrum since this set covers all our architecture and scalability needs (in addition to our existing access to resources).

3.2 Porting Effort

Given the discussion with respect to hardware in D7.7: Hardware Developments IV[4], we focus our efforts on cluster-type systems (with latest architectures) and accelerators. Our primary development hardware has been JURECA, an Intel and NVidia based cluster system with both GPUs and a KNL *booster*² (see Section 3.1.1).

The initial porting effort mainly involves porting the E-CAM workflow and configuring the application for the software stack of the target system. In particular, the applications are incorporated into EasyBuild with the dependencies provided by it. This ensures that knowledge gained during this process can be easily communicated to the wider community. The performance analysis workflow can then provide information to assist tuning the application for the target platform.

²The booster module is intended to accelerate calculations on a cluster module. Complex parts of the code, which are difficult to calculate simultaneously on a large number of processors, are executed on the so-called cluster module with simpler parts of the program that can be processed in parallel with greater efficiency transferred to the booster module.

3.2.1 Adding an LLVM-based toolchain to EasyBuild

The LLVM compiler infrastructure is extremely powerful and the addition of an LLVM-based compiler toolchain to EasyBuild would seem timely given the frequent use of the Clang compiler in particular. E-CAM has added a number of additional features to EasyBuild in order to support this initiative:

- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1729](#) and [EasyBuild Merge Request 8284](#) enable GPU offloading within Clang if CUDA is included as a dependency;
- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1717](#) adds support for building the Clang C++ standard library as part of the installation, and for using the Clang implementation of run-time type identification (RTTI)
- [EasyBuild Merge Request 1716](#) and [EasyBuild Merge Request 8335](#) add support for the LLVM-based Fortran compiler Flang to EasyBuild

The definition of the toolchain itself has been delayed due to the fact that the current implementation of the Flang compiler has been replaced by the F18 compiler (a ground-up implementation of a Fortran front end written in modern C++). This version of Flang was included in the main LLVM 11.0 release in 2020, but is still widely not considered production ready.

3.2.2 Testsuite failures in numpy/scipy

The widely-used Python packages `numpy` and `scipy` report failures in their testsuites but do not raise errors for these failures. For automated installation and testing, such as that done by EasyBuild, this means that these failures can pass unnoticed, hidden within log files. In [EasyBuild Merge Request 1744](#), we introduce the ability to catch these errors by default.

3.3 HTC Optimisation Collaboration with PRACE

While many HTC platforms/libraries exist (such as [Dask.distributed](#), [Celery](#) or [COMP Superscalar](#)), we failed to find one that was easy to use, targeted directly to cluster systems and flexible enough to handle MPI workloads. For this reason we embarked on a development project in collaboration with PRACE that builds on top of [Dask-Jobqueue](#) (which in turn leverages `Dask.distributed`). This approach has allowed us to pursue what is effectively interactive supercomputing, where micro-scheduled workloads are created within a Python environment (potentially in real time through an environment such as a Jupyter notebook).

The initial motivation for this library was driven by the ensemble-type calculations that are required in many scientific fields, and in particular in the materials science domain in which the E-CAM Centre of Excellence operates. The scope for parallelisation potential is best contextualised by the [Dask documentation](#):

A common approach to parallel execution in user-space is task scheduling. In task scheduling we break our program into many medium-sized tasks or units of computation, often a function call on a non-trivial amount of data. We represent these tasks as nodes in a graph with edges between nodes if one task depends on data produced by another. We call upon a task scheduler to execute this graph in a way that respects these data dependencies and leverages parallelism where possible, multiple independent tasks can be run simultaneously.

Many solutions exist. This is a common approach in parallel execution frameworks. Often task scheduling logic hides within other larger frameworks (Luigi, Storm, Spark, IPython Parallel, and so on) and so is often reinvented.

Dask is a specification that encodes task schedules with minimal incidental complexity using terms common to all Python projects, namely dicts, tuples, and callables. Ideally this minimum solution is easy to adopt and understand by a broad community.

While we were attracted by this approach, Dask did not support *task-level* parallelisation (in particular multi-node tasks). We researched other options (including Celery, PyCOMPSs, IPyParallel and others) and organised a workshop that explored some of these (see [the event website](#) for further details).

The initial idea for the implementation of this project was to use `MPI_Comm_spawn`, which is a collective call and spawns a child MPI job with n processes from within an MPI task. The problem with this is that, while part of the MPI standard, the implementation of this is highly specific to the MPI implementation itself, with a considerable amount of configuration information hidden (and often undocumented) in the `MPI_Info` argument to this call. That this information is not part of the standard means that the approach is highly non-portable, potentially requiring source code edits on all platforms where it is used. Not only this, but it was also our experience that, given its relative obscurity, it is not actually implemented at all in some cases (since it requires coupling to the resource manager, of which there are many possibilities).

Ultimately, once we came to discover the existence of the Dask extension `dask_jobqueue`, we realised that it would be possible for us to build upon its functionality to include support for parallel task workloads without having to resort to such *exotic* MPI functionality.

The approach described in the rest of this document allows for multi-level parallelisation (at the task level and at the framework level) while leveraging all the pre-existing effort within the Dask framework (such as scheduling, resilience, data management and resource scaling).

The resulting library is flexible, scalable, efficient and adaptive. It is capable of simultaneously utilising CPUs, KNL and GPUs and dynamically adjusting its use of these resources based on the resource requirements of the scheduled task workload. The ultimate scalability and hardware capabilities of the solution is dictated by the scalability characteristics of the tasks themselves (if there are 100 nodes per task with GPUs, then the library can carry out N of these at once depending on resource availability for a total of $100 * N$ nodes).

In January 2020, E-CAM succeeded in acquiring PRACE Preparatory Access Type C, evaluated at the 39th cut-off date (02/12/2019). This project includes 6 months of PM effort from PRACE experts and allowed us to continue our development collaboration with PRACE into the final year of the E-CAM project.

4 Modules and Application Codes

For the modules and application codes that have been available and selected in the project, we provide the following information on a per-WP basis:

- Relevance to E-CAM (including relevant modules and ESDWs);
- Relevant porting, benchmarks and scaling analysis details.

Note that, in this deliverable, there are no modules from WP3 since there was no PDRA in that WP for a significant portion of relevant reporting period. Instead, we have included 4 modules from WP4.

Where possible timing measurements are taken using internal timers available within the applications themselves. If no such feature is available, or it is more appropriate, then the CPU time reported by the resource management system of the HPC resource is used.

4.1 WP1: Classical Molecular Dynamics

In the previous iteration of this set of deliverables [5] we introduced the [jobqueue_features](#) HTC library whose development is driven by the ensemble-type calculations that are required in many scientific fields, and in particular in the materials science domain. A concrete example is the study of molecular dynamics with atomistic detail, where timesteps must be used on the order of a femto-second. Many problems in biological chemistry and materials science involve events that only spontaneously occur after a millisecond or longer (for example, biomolecular conformational changes). That means that around 10^{12} time steps would be needed to see a single millisecond-scale event: the problem of "rare events" in theoretical and computational chemistry. Modern supercomputers are beginning to make it possible to obtain trajectories long enough to observe some of these processes, but to fully characterize a transition with proper statistics, many examples are needed. In such cases the same peta-scale application must be run many thousands of times with varying inputs.

In this deliverable, we highlight additional developments of [jobqueue_features](#) and the scalability of those developments.

4.1.1 Relevance for E-CAM

Committer analysis is a powerful, but computationally expensive, tool to study reaction mechanisms in complex systems. The main goal of this effort is to facilitate an implementation of committer analysis in the software application [OpenPathSampling](#) (OPS) that is performance portable across a range of HPC hardware and hosting sites.

The committer can also be used to generate initial trajectories for transition path sampling, a less-expensive technique to study reaction mechanisms. The software developed here is being used to generate initial trajectories to study a conformational change in the main protease of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which causes COVID-19 (this is a modification from the original goal when the project was conceived). This conformational change may regulate the accessibility of the active site of the main protease, and a better understanding of its mechanism could aid drug design.

Committer analysis is essentially an ensemble calculation that maps straightforwardly to an HTC workflow, where typical individual tasks have moderate scalability and indefinite duration. Since this workflow requires dynamic and resilient scalability within the HTC framework, OPS is coupled to the custom HTC library [jobqueue_features](#).

4.1.2 HTC with [jobqueue_features](#)

Initial development of the [jobqueue_features](#) library (whose source code can be found on the [jobqueue_features](#) [GitHub repository](#)) had two major aspects, one that targeted a simplified user experience (minimising configuration and implementation overhead for the end user) and the other that targeted leveraging the hardware heterogeneity of a resource such as [JURECA](#).

Current development targets porting the custom HTC library to a wider variety of HPC platforms (specifically additional resource managers and MPI runtimes) and stress testing the framework for very large task counts.

Both OPS and [jobqueue_features](#) are Python-based and we have also developed more sophisticated support for Python-based MPI-enabled tasks, including direct access to the memory space of executed tasks to avoid the use of filesystems for data transfer. The first module we use as the reference point for this deliverable relates to the development of this capability within the library (see [WP1 Merge Request 237](#)).

The library is primarily accessed through a set of Python decorators: `on_cluster`, `task` and `mpi_task`. The `on_cluster` decorator gets or creates *clusters*, which in turn submit worker resource allocation requests to the scheduler to execute tasks. The `mpi_task` decorator derives from `task` and enhances it with MPI specific settings (e.g. the MPI runtime and related settings).

```

1 lammps_cluster = CustomSLURMCluster(
2     # Request MPI mode and define resources
3     mpi_mode=True, nodes=2, ntasks_per_node=12,
4     # Set execution environment
5     env_extra=["module restore lammps_tutorial" ],
6 )
7
8 @mpi_task(cluster_id=lammps_cluster.name)
9 def lammps_task(input_file, run_steps=100):
10     from mpi4py import MPI
11     from lammps import PyLammps
12
13     L = PyLammps()      # Initialise LAMMPS
14     L.file(input_file) # Read the input file
15     L.run(run_steps)   # Simulate the system
16     if MPI.COMM_WORLD.Get_rank() == 0:
17         return "Potential energy: %s" % L.eval("pe")
18
19 @on_cluster(cluster=lammps_cluster)
20 def my_lammps_job(input_file="in.melt", run_steps=100):
21     t1 = lammps_task(input_file, run_steps=run_steps)
22     print(t1.result()) # blocking call (t1 is a future)

```

Listing 1: Example of decorator usage to parallelize computation

In Listing 1 we show a minimal, but complete, example which uses the `mpi_task` and `on_cluster` decorators for a LAMMPS execution. The configuration, communication and serialization is isolated and hidden from user code. Any call to `my_lammps_job` results in the `lammps_task` function being executed remotely by a `lammps_cluster` worker allocated by the resource manager with 2 nodes and 12 MPI tasks per node. The code can be executed interactively in a Jupyter notebook. To overlap calculations one would need to return the `t1 future`³ rather than the actual result.

The second module we use as reference is [Merge Request 249](#), which adds support for additional MPI runtimes to make the library a more portable solution between HPC systems.

Strong and weak scalability

Strong and weak scaling are undefined for an HTC use case. To draw some equivalence, one could say that strong scaling would correspond to the ability of the individual tasks to scale to larger resource usage. Such a measure as this is entirely dependent on the scalability of the applications used within the tasks themselves rather than related to the HTC framework. In the case of OPS, it uses an underlying community application engine to achieve scalability. We have tested the framework with both GROMACS (as used within OPS) and LAMMPS (in particular PyLAMMPS). Neither of these applications are directly under the remit of this project and, as heavily-used community applications, both are known to scale well on HPC resources.

Another argument that could be made is that strong scaling could be defined as the number of simultaneous workers that the framework can utilise. Since each worker is an individual job, the limitation here doesn't come from the framework, it is the number of simultaneous jobs that can be allocated by the resource manager for a single user (which is usually of $O(100)$ but varies from site to site). Since job submissions are ultimately handled by the library dependency [dask_jobqueue](#), we must wait for [support of job arrays](#) to be able to reliably perform any such analysis.

Our interest lies in the scalability of the HTC framework itself with respect to task counts. We would argue that is somewhat equivalent to a weak scaling analysis when considering an HTC workload: higher task count is equivalent to larger workload and triggers the dynamic provisioning of additional workers by the HTC framework. We include here the data relevant to that analysis.

The `jobqueue_features` library had not been stress-tested for the number of tasks it was capable of supporting. Previous efforts had looked at up to 2000 tasks, in our tests for this deliverable (and as part of the collaborative project with PRACE) we scaled out to one million tasks on all available architectures (JUWELS for SkyLake, Irene Joliot-Curie for SkyLake and KNL), with each individual task using 2 nodes worth of resources. Each set of 2 nodes forms a worker with the amount of workers allocated by the resource manager are reused by various tasks. The number of workers that the framework can use is entirely dependent on the maximum number of allowed simultaneous jobs by a specific site. The package can simultaneously use workers on different resource types (CPU, KNL, GPU,...), as we have previously shown for the JURECA system.

As seen in Fig. 2 (and in Table 1), the overhead of the framework is negligible at ~1ms per task for SkyLake architecture and ~10ms per task for KNL architecture. Note that this overhead is completely independent of the resource usage of the workers themselves.

³A *future* is an object that acts as a proxy for a result that is initially unknown, usually because the computation of its value is not yet complete

Figure 2: Overhead of the HTC framework per task as the number of tasks is varied. For JUWELS and IRENE (SKL) the overhead plateaus at ~1ms, for IRENE (KNL) the plateau is ~10ms.

Tasks	Overhead per task (seconds, excluding node configuration)		
	JUWELS	IRENE (KNL)	IRENE (SKL)
10	0.8899	2.7884	0.6899
100	0.0199	0.2896	0.0699
1000	0.0039	0.0347	0.0069
10000	0.0053	0.0548	0.0017
20000	0.0026	0.2076	0.0168
50000	0.0008	0.0181	0.0092
100000	0.0008	0.0133	0.0011
200000	0.0007	0.0175	0.0010
1000000	0.0007	0.0152	0.0011

Table 1: Overhead of the HTC framework per task as the number of tasks is varied

We also note that the configuration times of the nodes to prepare them for job execution vary by architecture, but are far more substantial, see Table 2.

	JUWELS	IRENE (KNL)	IRENE (SKL)
Node configuration time (per worker)	10	29	6

Table 2: Time (in seconds) to configure node for job execution

UCX Protocol

We also tested the efficiency of the UCX protocol⁴ in comparison to TCPoIB (TCP over InfiniBand) for communication within the framework. We used several test cases with different kinds of computation, from basic hand written functions to those based on functions provided by Dask. On most of these tests, UCX performance is not very different to TCPoIB performance. In general, UCX does give slightly better results for tasks based on Dask functions and TCPoIB performs better for hand written tasks (most likely due to the fact that Dask can perform optimisations when it has control over the data objects). Critically, UCX has been seen to lead to some errors related to the fact that it is not yet a fully supported technology within Dask. In particular, during tests there were problems in the case of restarting the workers while UCX was in use, which means that we potentially lose resiliency in this scenario. Given the very limited potential for performance improvement and the significant impact of sacrificing resiliency, we would not recommend the use of UCX with `jobqueue_features` (or even Dask) at this time.

⁴Unified Communication X (UCX) provides an optimized communication layer for Message Passing (MPI), PGAS/OpenSHMEM libraries and RPC/data-centric applications.

4.2 WP2: Electronic Structure

In the Electronic Structure work package (WP2) the field is particularly well-developed with a number of heavily utilised community codes (some of which, such as Quantum ESPRESSO and SIESTA, are already the subject matter of another CoE). Within E-CAM, the main focus is more on providing utilities so that they can be leveraged by a wider spectrum of applications as libraries, which is an effort coordinated and sustained by the [Electronic Structure Library \(ESL\)](#).

In this deliverable we focus on the development of a software package, [PANNA](#), that provides a comprehensive toolkit for creating neural network models for atomistic systems.

4.2.1 Relevance for E-CAM

In WP2 (and similarly in WP4), E-CAM is keen to support the development of packages that take advantage of modern developments in AI and machine learning (both with respect to the theoretical advancements and the software implementations that leverage them). The [PANNA](#) toolkit benefits from the optimisation and hardware-flexibility of the underlying TensorFlow engine which allows it to be used on multiple CPU/GPU/TPU systems, making it possible to develop and optimise neural network models based on large datasets.

4.2.2 PANNA: Properties from Artificial Neural Network Architectures

The [PANNA](#) toolkit was developed from scratch within the lifetime of E-CAM, with 5 modules contributed to the [E-CAM library](#). In Fig. 3 (reproduced from [6]), we show and explain the basic workflow of the PANNA toolkit to create a neural network (based on input from an ab initio code such as Quantum Espresso) that can be used as a potential by a classical MD code (such as LAMMPS).

Figure 3: PANNA workflow. Top layer corresponds to user intervention in the neural network potential generation process. Input and network hyperparameters are determined at this layer. Currently several helper programs (not shown) included in the PANNA package aim to help users in this intervention. In principle, the hyperparameters are also part of the network optimization process and can potentially become an automated part of the workflow. Yellow boxes indicate main programs in PANNA while white boxes stand for the user-owned data in different stages of processing and the network potential. The interface with the third party codes are established via parser scripts and patches (not shown) included in the package.

For the connection to WP7, we reference the [neural network training module \(Merge Request 223\)](#) and the [neural network evaluation module \(Merge Request 220\)](#). These modules represent how the [PANNA](#) toolkit benefits from the optimisation and hardware-flexibility of the underlying TensorFlow engine which allows it to be used on multiple CPU/GPU/TPU systems, making it possible to develop and optimise neural network models based on large datasets.

There is no practical use in WP7 evaluating the performance of TensorFlow since its capabilities, and limitations, when it comes to the use of large-scale resources are well known (and [documented by TensorFlow itself](#)). What we wish to highlight is the effort that the EasyBuild project (to which E-CAM contributes extensively) has gone to support the building of the TensorFlow from source for target architectures. In particular, we note that [TensorFlow has one of the most heavily customised installation workflows in EasyBuild](#). This includes support for the installation of TensorFlow *from source* on Intel, AMD, ARM and POWER9 architectures.

The significance, and impact, of this should not be underestimated since in our tests we have seen that, for example, the POWER9 chip running TensorFlow has comparable performance to the V100 GPU when using an optimised build. Such results are encouraging for users that may not necessarily have access to the latest GPUs. It is also true that, by default, TensorFlow does not provide a fat build for all CUDA compute capabilities. This may result in TensorFlow not being optimised for the available GPU. In such cases, building TensorFlow with the compute capabilities of the available GPU on the system can also have a significant performance impact.

With respect to scalability, PANNA acts as key component in a multi-scale workflow that connects the results of an ab initio code (a scalable example of which is Quantum Espresso) to a classical MD code (a scalable example of which is LAMMPS) via a neural network model potential. The impact of PANNA being limited by the scalability of TensorFlow is mitigated by the fact that, in the overall workflow, PANNA consumes a relatively small amount of the compute resources.

4.3 WP4: Meso- and Multi-scale Modelling

The DL_MESO code, and its porting to GPUs, has consistently featured in WP7 deliverables. In this deliverable, as part of the WP4 contribution, the following two modules are presented: benchmarking DL_MESO on multi-GPU nodes up to 4096 GPUs (see [Merge Request 78](#)) and the use of the ALL library for improved load balancing in DL_MESO (see [Merge Request 180](#)).

Also related to WP4, we include a [ParaDiS](#) case study, the reference modules for which are the development of an [extension of the ParaDiS DDD code where dislocation/precipitate interactions are included](#) and the [optimisation of ParaDiS for the Cray XC40 cluster at CSC](#) in Finland (both of these modules are part of [Merge Request 38](#) in the E-CAM library).

4.3.1 Relevance for E-CAM

The DL_MESO_DPD porting to a multi-GPU environment can be seen as an extension of the Pilot Project developed by the E-CAM PDRA Dr. Silvia Chiacchiera in WP4 on [Polarizable Soft Water Model](#). The main purpose is to accelerate the DL_MESO_DPD code when electric particles (like polarised water) are added to the system. Charged particles require the evaluation of long range interaction forces, notoriously expensive due to the complexity of the algorithms used (like the Smoothed Particle Mesh Ewald method). A GPU-enabled version of the code would allow the user to run large system of charged particles even on a simple workstation. The project involves a collaboration between computational scientists (STFC Daresbury), academia (University of Manchester), and industry (Unilever).

The ALL library has been introduced during the E-CAM Extended Software Development Workshop for Meso and Multi Scale Modelling hosted in Jülich in June 2019. It is made of a series of modules of different load balance techniques for particles methods ranging from simple *Tensor-Product* method to more sophisticated *Voronoi Mesh* method. Releases of the ALL library are available for download from the [ALL git repository](#).

The wider aim of the E-CAM project is to develop sophisticated software infrastructure required to fully exploit the capabilities of the emerging generation of supercomputing technologies. This involves optimisation of codes on the new architectures. Moreover, bleeding edge research often encounters the problem of the need to extend the feature list of research codes without sacrificing their computational feasibility. These are the cases studied using the ParaDiS code within this deliverable.

4.3.2 Increasing the scalability of DL_MESO_DPD

Benchmarking DL_MESO_DPD on multi-GPU on [Piz Daint](#)

We previously presented in Deliverable III [5] the weak and strong scaling up to 2048 GPUs with 1.8 billion particles. In this module we extended the scaling to 4096 GPUs. However, the test case is slightly different: we used a binary mixture which tends to separate in two immiscible liquids (like oil and water, see [Figure 4](#)).

A final paper has been submitted and accepted by Computer Physics Communications [7].

[Figure 5](#) shows good efficiency (>85%) for the strong scaling. The plot shows a comparison with same scaling without overlap between communication and computation which highlights the importance of a correct implementation of the CUDA streams used. Moreover, the memory footprint ([figure 6](#) shows how we fully occupy the GPU memory with 256 GPUs and have only 10% utilised with 4096. Despite the relatively low occupancy, results are still satisfactory.

Further details on the implementation of these improvements and the source code can be found in the E-CAM GitLab service under the linked [Merge Request 78](#).

Figure 4: Phase separation at different time steps

Figure 5: DL_MESO_GPU strong scaling up to 4096 GPUs.

Figure 6: DL_MESO_GPU memory usage for strong scaling up to 4096 GPUs

Load balancing for multi-GPU DL_MESO

This module concerns the implementation of the ALL library for load balancing in the multi-GPU version of DL_MESO_DPD. The intention is to allow for better performance when modelling complex systems, like large proteins or lipid bilayers, redistributing the workload across the GPUs. Due to the orthogonal domain decomposition used in DL_MESO, we used the Tensor-Product method which works well for non-staggered orthogonal meshes. We update the new coordinates at every time step, if required, according to default relaxation control γ value defined in the ALL library.

Figure 7: Load imbalance in DL_MESO with ALL library for a water drop between two surfaces. Each colour represent a different domain assigned to a different GPU: *a)* top view, *b)* perspective view, *c)* front view, *d)* load balance vs time.

A test case was implemented (see Figure 7 *a)*, *b)*, and *c)*) that reproduces 32k water beads initially scattered along a regular structure and then slowly agglomerating towards an unique large drop confined between two parallel surfaces. The system is divided across 8 GPUs and, for the purposes of the visualisation, we restrict ourselves to 32k particles. For a larger number of particles it would not be possible to simulate the system without load-balancing, since all the particles agglomerate to a subset of the available GPUs and one or more GPUs would run out of memory having to accommodate a large number of particles. Moreover, such a strong load imbalance drastically reduces the scalability of the application.

In Figure 7 *d)* we see the time history of the load imbalance for each GPU when using the ALL library. Without load balancing the system would gradually diverge from the ideal value of 12.5%. You can find a video that shows the evolution of the load-balancing for this system in [another related Merge Request](#).

Further details on the implementation of ALL library in DL_MESO and the source code can be found in the E-CAM GitLab service under the linked [Merge Request 180](#).

4.3.3 ParaDiS precipitate and porting to HPC systems

The code optimization work has involved codes for mesoscale modeling of crystalline and amorphous systems. ParaDiS is a free large scale dislocation dynamics simulation code to study the fundamental mechanisms of plasticity. It was originally developed at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. It is written in C (with a little C++) and uses the MPI library for communication between processors. It runs routinely on 100-1000 processors and scalability on 132,000 processors of BlueGene/L has been demonstrated.

During the E-CAM project, new features allowing for the simulation of immobile spherical precipitates pinning the movement of dislocations was implemented into the ParaDiS Discrete dislocation dynamics (DDD) code. There the dislocations interact with the precipitates via a Gaussian potential, generating a normal force acting on the dislocation segments. The problem statement in 3D predicts a computationally untractable problem exhibiting the dynamics of

long-range interacting elements.

The method extended a recent version of the ParaDiS code to handle the presence of pinning centers. These work as localized Gaussian potentials that interact with the near-by dislocations as detailed in [8]. An additional "disorder field" defining the locations of the precipitates in 3D and the interactions parametrized by the impurity strength (which may vary from precipitate to another) and the range of the Gaussian potential (which also may vary) are given as an input to the program. The dislocation dynamics is handled as in the "vanilla" ParaDiS with an additional force term that accounts for each dislocation segment for the nearby impurities.

Figure 8: Example simulation of 3D dislocation dynamics with precipitates included. Figure adapted from [1].

The module thus allows to study various precipitate fields (density, geometry, strength, interaction range) as desired. In a typical ParaDiS simulation one does a simulation of the response of a dislocation system to a strain/stress protocol. The starting point is a dislocation system, which has been obtained from relaxing a random or patterned configuration under zero external stress until the evolution becomes negligible. In the presence of impurities the customary approach is to do two relaxation steps: first follow the relaxation of dislocation configuration, then add the disorder field to that and re-relax.

In the current version apart from HPC-related parallelization-relevant steps the subroutines SegSegForce (segment-to-segment force calculation) and FMSigma2Core2 (force multipole expansion) are well vectorized, and the code now also uses better multiple threads in their context. The runtimes as a function of the number of nodes before and after optimizations is reported in Figure 9 showing that for large-scale jobs speed-ups of a factor of 1.5 and allows to use more computational nodes than what is reasonable with the original version, so that the production times speeded up by a factor of two.

ParaDiS with Intel Cascade Lake

Optimal porting of ParaDiS with precipitates to systems with Intel Cascade Lake CPUs similar to the Puhti supercomputer at CSC were also investigated. By finding the best compiler and the most optimal compiler optimization flags, especially to select the optimal vector instruction set for the platform and the code, the performance of the application can be increased significantly. For example, with Intel compilers one can decrease the run time by approximately 25% by using the AVX-512 vector instructions instead of the defaults.

ParaDiS with AMD Zen2

For AMD Rome CPUs, similar to the Mahti supercomputer at CSC, finding the best compiler and the most optimal compiler optimizations for ParaDiS on the Zen2 architecture so that the code can be run more efficiently was also investigated. Good performance can be achieved both with GNU and Intel compilers by using an optimal combination of compiler optimization options and vector instructions. For example, with GNU compilers one can decrease the run time by approximately 21% by using the optimized compiler options.

Figure 9: The scalability of the modified ParaDis code on the Cray XC40 (with 36 Broadwell cores on each compute node) before and after optimization.

5 Outlook

In the final deliverable of WP7 we will showcase the cross-cutting development efforts and applications with more potential in terms of extreme scalability. In particular, we expect to report additional results relating to the [jobqueue_features](#) HTC library and to the load-balancing library being developed at JSC.

In collaboration with [FocusCoE](#), WP7 is contributing to a workshop on co-design scheduled to take place during the [EuroHPC Summit Week \(EHPCSW\) 2021](#).

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Acronyms Used

HPC	High Performance Computing
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe
ESDW	Extended Software Development Workshop
WP	Work Package
CoE	Centre of Excellence
PDRA	Post-doctoral Research Associate
HTC	High Throughput Computing
ESL	Electronic Structure Library
DDD	Discrete dislocation dynamics

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